

FEATURES OF THE USAGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Choriqulov Rustamjon Ibodullo ugli

Navoi University of innovation

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8083052>

Abstract. *To this day, thanks to education through digital technologies, educational methods are being facilitated for those who receive education. In this case, the role of educational system Vosti is performed by multimedias, codescopes, computers, laptops, internet-connected TVs, telephone lines, smart boards, projectors. Tutoring educators with such tools provides an improvement in the quality of Education. Therefore, in this article, the features of the use of digital technologies in improving the quality of education were widely covered by the author.*

Keywords: *digital technology, quality education, information retrieval and use, IT industry, multimedias, codoscope, computer, laptop, internet-connected TVs, telephone lines, smart whiteboard, projector, online classes.*

INTRODUCTION

To date, education and education in the world are becoming one of the pressing issues. Because it is no longer a secret to whom Hecht, it is quality education that plays an important role in saving the world in which we live from various problems. Therefore, many countries are now investing heavily in the education sector. In this regard, significant work has also been carried out in our country.

Despite this, there are a number of issues in our education system that are still waiting for a solution that cannot be said about modern quality education without eliminating them. In particular, in the current period, when the speed of obtaining and using information is very popular, we think that it is impossible to improve the quality of education and educate socially active youth without involving digital technologies in the educational system. We have previously conducted educational programs in the traditional way, that is, in the form of a lecture. This was also done through large-scale Hajj books and manuals. This in turn did not ensure that the quality of education was so high. Students were also forced to carry large volume literature and large baggy bags in order to master various additional materials. Now the process of digitization of Education has begun.

Digital technology is one modern form of business, in which a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing serve as the main factor in production and management. The use of the results obtained in practice, on the other hand, allows you to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of enema. Examples include automatic production processes of various types, 3D-technology, cloud technology, remote medicine services, production and delivery of products using smart technologies, storage of goods of various types and their sale processes. We will dwell on this article instead of digitization in the educational system.

The methods of education are becoming easier for learners if they are educated through digital technology. In this case, the role of educational system Vosti is performed by multimedias, codescopes, computers, laptops, internet-connected TVs, telephone lines, smart boards, projectors. Tutoring educators with such tools provides an improvement in the quality of Education. It is

known to us that the use of digital technologies in online classes will work well. For example, we can assume that online lessons given through television are a form of digital education.

Hence, in digital education:

- has the opportunity to receive education wherever and whenever you want;
- a culture of obtaining and using information from the internet is formed;
- raises the education system to a new level;
- dramatically reduces time and spending;
- Those like not getting lost in the “digital world” and having advantages in finding a good job.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Automation of educational management through the use of information and communication technologies during the new development of our country, further development of electronic resources and distance education, special attention is paid by the head of state to the popularization of professions in IT among education recipients, shows how high the role and importance of digital technologies are in the educational system.

It is difficult to imagine our daily life without information communication technologies, computers and the Internet in the era when today’s globalization process is taking place. That is why today, digital technologies are gradually entering all areas of our daily life and becoming an integral part of social life. It is also a sign that digital technologies are of great importance not only in such areas as economics, politics, but also in the educational system, as well as in the fact that higher education institutions are established in our country, which train more than 10 specialists in the field of technology and digital technologies.

As the main reason for the popularization of the use of digital technologies in the educational system, we can show the presence of their side, which is convenient not only for educators, but also for students. For example, students will be able to receive education at any point and whenever they want. In addition, through the use of digital technologies in education, we have the following:

- first of all, in regions where there is a shortage of pedagogical personnel, students can also be educated online or in a distance form;
- secondly, to obtain, search, disseminate and use information about the subject they want from the internet of teachers and students;
- thirdly, on the basis of the use of digital technologies in the system, to increase the efficiency of education, reduce the cost of time and funds;
- fourth, through the application of digital technology to the educational process, we get opportunities not only for students to master the subjects, but also for the extent to which they are mastering knowledge and are ready for problem situations, and for the formation of critical thinking in them, as well as the orientation of students to develop their ability to work on their own independently.

The main factor that today digital technology is actively entering the educational process is that it is of particular importance with its effectiveness in changing the quality of classes in a positive way. In the further improvement of such quality levels, the development of new strategic projects for the application of various means of training and digital technologies and the improvement of regulatory legal acts of introduction into the industry, the establishment of training

rooms, laboratories, centers containing digital devices with high efficiency will serve as an important factor.

The rise of the digital education system is also greatly served by the opening of Wi-Fi zones and IT parks. The opportunity arises for educators to grow their ability to work with digital technologies and to organize various open courses through the internet. This in turn makes educators work more on themselves and further increase the quality of education due to competition.

Moreover, if the implementation of digital technologies, namely artificial intelligence technology, is used not only in the educational system, but also in other areas, in particular, to detect tax evasion cases, prevent fraud, automate data analysis and repetitive processes, and increase transparency, large-scale data — Big data, on the other hand, offers tax authorities the opportunity to store, process, better predict receipts, and improve document exchange between payers and tax authorities.

Mastering digital technologies is happening faster than other innovations in the history of mankind: in just twenty years, digital technologies have managed to cover almost 50% of the population of developing countries and, with their help, transform societies.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his address to the Supreme Assembly of 2020: “to achieve progress, we need to master digital knowledge and modern information technologies *vas hart*. This gives us the opportunity to go the shortest path of the ascent”, they noted, it is not surprising that in our country they are intended not only to make a fundamental turn in the development of the digital economy, but also to introduce digital technologies into all spheres of social life, including the educational system.

DISCUSSION

Indeed, the development of the digital economy requires the effective and unimaginable use of digital technologies. In order to effectively use digital technologies, a specialist in such technologies requires personnel to have strong knowledge and experience. Mature specialist personnel needed inter-industry are trained at training camps. Therefore, the introduction of digital technologies into the educational system serves as a necessary factor in the realization of our goals. In further improving the activities aimed at the implementation of digital technologies in all areas of the educational system, referring to these goals in order to raise our country, the following:

➤ first of all, to further increase the speed of the Internet in our country and increase the quality of communication to a high level, in a word, the high level of provision of services provided by the Internet social network;

➤ secondly, in order to ensure a strong integration between digital technologies and educational technologies and the IT sector, to create additional conditions for further improvement of activities aimed at the continuous development of professional skills of pedagogical personnel in this regard;

➤ thirdly, it is necessary to successfully solve such tasks as the regular Organization of courses aimed at improving the skills of teachers in creating interactive multimedia presentations designed for lectures or seminar classes on topics that embody the importance and useful aspects of it and digital technologies and procedures for their use. Only then can we achieve knowledge to young people at the level of today’s requirements by introducing and using digital technologies into the educational system and applying them in practice.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above points, it can be concluded that the use of digital technologies in the education system, firstly, ensures the effectiveness of teaching, secondly, the preparation of various illustrations, videos, visual aids, handouts related to the lesson processes, and thirdly, the teacher - serves to improve the skills of pedagogues in the use of multimedia products, computer equipment, Internet tools and their use in the course of the lesson.

REFERENCES

1. M.M.Xolmuxammedov. "Professional ta'lim tizimini zamonaviy yondashuvlar asosida modernizatsiya qilish". Uzlusiz ta'lim ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal. 2021. 6-son. 3-4-betlar.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 6-noyabrdagi "O'zbekistonning yangi taraqqiyot davrida ta'lim-tarbiya va ilm-fan sohalarini rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-6108-son Farmoni.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга мурожаатномаси, Халқ сўзи 2020 йил 25 январь.
4. J.Oripov, O.To'xtayev. "Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning dolzarb jihatlari va ahamiyati". Science and Innovation international scientific journal volume 1 issue 6. 2022.
5. Yuldashev, U.A., Xudoyberdiev, M.Z., & Axmedov, T.B. (2021). O'quv jarayonining sifatini oshirishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish. //Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 1262-1268